

THE MYTH AND ITS ESSENCE IN UZBEK FOLKLORE STUDIES

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Abstract. In the following article, the myth and its essence of Uzbek folklore, as well as their classification and the stages of their gradual development, were considered and analyzed.

Keywords: myth, Uzbek folklore, history, image, development

A myth is a complex of ancient people's primitive ideas about existence, the creation of the universe, the creation of man, plants and animals, the appearance of heavenly bodies, the causes and essence of natural phenomena, mythical heroes, gods and goddesses. which included religious views. The ancient man, who had not yet separated himself from nature, tried to interpret and explain the reasons for the appearance of material existence around him by means of mythological imaginations. A myth is an expression of an ancient man's unconscious emotional relationship to reality, and it is the oldest series of ideas that explain the essence of various aspects of nature and social life. Although mythological imaginations explain the essence of a certain reality by means of fictional fiction, at the place where the myth was created and popularized, it was accepted by its creator and performers as a description of the events that actually happened.

The ancient man's understanding of nature and perception of reality is a very complex phenomenon of thought. Our ancestors tried to understand the mysteries of the material world surrounding them, to understand the essence of natural phenomena, and accepted the whole existence as it is. The use of imagery and poetic symbols in the perception of reality in the material world is a characteristic feature of artistic creation and is based on a conscious emotional response to reality. The emergence of material existence in the world, the causes of certain natural phenomena, issues of nature and human relations were interpreted in a mythological way in the mind of ancient people. Based on these oldest beliefs about the universe, the system of the first mythological imaginations was born. Mahmud Koshgari in his work "Devonu Luğotit Turk" "sav." explains the word. Scientists say that this word is one of the first words spoken by our ancestors. And "to fight" is to talk, remembering the words of the fathers. So, the word "sav" also has an aspect close to the meaning of myth. A

myth is an expression of an ancient man's unconscious emotional relationship to reality.

According to the dictionary and encyclopedias, the word "totemism" is derived from "his clan". One of the tribes living in North America believed that there is a blood relationship between people and certain types of animals and plants. Those animals were not hunted, killed, and their meat was not eaten. And the plants are revered. This custom exists in the beliefs of all the peoples of the world and is preserved to this day. Animals such as horses, sheep, goats, birds such as geese, ducks, swallows, and fowls are revered as totem animals among the Turks.

The word "fetishism" is recorded in dictionaries and encyclopedias as meaning "feitico" in Portuguese and "fetiche" in French - something magical. It is based on the ancient people's understanding that inanimate objects have a divine quality. It is known that during life, a person lives in relationship with the sun, moon, stars, mountains, and water without knowing it. The sun and water are especially important in human destiny. Our ancestors, who lived in ancient times, considered things such as knives, bread, stoves, ovens, caps, books, and especially arrows and bows to be sacred.

In the concept of fetishism, in addition to various objects, colors and dreams are preserved. Colors such as white, black, blue, green, red, purple have a specific meaning. The green, white, blue, red between them, the moon in the corner and 12 stars on the flag of Uzbekistan all have symbolic meanings. Usually, green represents youth, red, spilled blood on the one hand, girlish pride on the other, white life, black, tragedy on the one hand, greatness, majesty, maturity, adulthood on the other. made

"Animism" is derived from the Latin word "anima", and it is emphasized in scientific literature that it means soul, soul. According to animism, our ancient ancestors knew that everything in the world has a soul. In primitive times, man was considered to consist of body and soul. They also thought that a person dies when the soul leaves the body. This concept is applied to everything. That is why it is better to connect belief in the phenomena of totemism and fetishism in mythology, the religious attitude to their existence with animism. To put it more simply, a person's belief in the phenomena of totemism and fetishism is manifested in animism in a harmonious state. Using the magical and miraculous power of the word to influence the human psyche, free it from illness, and give spiritual refreshment to its nature are the qualities of animism. That's why the meaning of folk bakhshis has been preserved, that is, giving healing.

Although mythological imaginations explain the creation of the world, the emergence of the flora and fauna, and the emergence of mankind through the means of fiction, the myth is evaluated by its creator and performers as a description of the events that took place. M.I. Steblin-Kamensky said that "myth is a description of a certain reality, no matter how fictitious the events described in it are, they are always accepted as an expression of truth, real reality, in the place where it was created and lived. Of course, the researcher who studies the myth does not believe in its fabrication. That is why the myth is not understood today as an expression of real life reality. In this way, the researcher's own vision of the myth, i.e. the view that "the myth is fiction" is created. In the place where it was created and popularized, the myth was understood as an expression of real reality.

In the Uzbek language, the mythological visions of our ancient ancestors expressed in a systematic form, expressed through words (telling stories), actions (ritual dances) and images (ancient artifacts, rock paintings, etc.) are called "asotir" in Uzbek. called by terms such as "myth". In the work of the great linguist Mahmud Koshgari, who lived in the 11th century, the concept of myth is expressed by the word "sav" in the work "Devonu lughotit Turk". This word means "message", "proverb", "story", "story", "word", "speech" in the ancient Turkic language. When Mahmud Koshgari collected material for his work, he also carefully studied the mythological imaginations of the Turkic tribes. This is confirmed by the fact that "Devon" contains the myth about "barok", a dog hatched from a bird's egg, and heavenly views about the stars of the Golden Pile (Iron Pile). "Kazunuq" is a stake. That is why the pole star is called "Temur Kazunuk". It means "iron stake". Because the sky revolves over it," writes Mahmud Koshgari. Commenting on the word "blue hornet", the scientist writes the following: "blue hornet is the name of a bird. It is said that this bird has two wings of steel, and it flies from one side to the other by hitting the mountain with its wing. This word was told to me by a person who used it myself.

It seems that in this mythological legend, the people's views about the imaginary bird, which exists in the folklore of the ancient Turks, have been expressed. In the Uzbek language, the description of a bird that has grown hard feathers as "the iron wing" seems to have preserved traces of these old ideas.

The ways of popularization of myths, which contain the ideas of our ancestors who lived in the past about the world, express their worldview and are intended to be passed down from generation to generation, are also different. That is, the myth is told based on the artistic form of the myth genre.

Mythological visions are represented as ritual games in primitive rites and ceremonies. Mythical plots are also reflected in the symbolic lines of antiques, works of art created on the basis of ancient imaginations, and works of folk crafts and applied art.

Myths that reflect the ancient fantastic concepts of our ancestors about the universe, natural phenomena and social life are divided into the following types:

1) myths about the beginning (myths about the creation of the universe and the emergence of life on earth);

2) heavenly myths (myths about the appearance of celestial bodies and natural phenomena;

3) anthropogenic myths (myths about mythical characters with unusual characteristics - for example, myths about Heracles, Gilgamesh, Odami Od, Hubbi);

4) cult myths (myths related to certain religious beliefs, for example, myths about fertility cult, water cult, plant cult, fire cult);

5) totemistic myths (based on ancient ideas about totemism);

6) calendar myths (myths related to the calculation of the year, month, day - for example, myths related to the calculation of Ayamajuz, Ahman-dahman, chilla, ninety);

7) myths about death and resurrection nature cults (for example, mythological plots about Siovush);

8) animistic myths (myths embodying ancient ideas about the soul):

9) manistic myths (myths about the patronage of ancestors);

10) dualistic myths (myths that reflect mystical views about the struggle between the forces of good and evil);

11) eschatological myths (myths about the end of the world, the end of time).

Mythology, which has acquired important practical importance as the first stage of the development of human thinking, is the basis of primitive culture, one of the ancient means of understanding the world, and the beginning of artistic thinking. Mythology is based on ancient myths about the universe, nature, man, heavenly bodies, objects and events.

The archaic layer of mythology includes solar, lunar and astral myths about the sun, moon and stars, celestial myths about the creation of the universe, anthropogenic myths about the creation of mankind, cultic, animistic and composed of myths. In the regions where farming culture was formed, calendar myths and myths about death and resurrection nature cults based on

symbolic and metaphorical interpretations of natural and climatic changes are widespread. In particular, mythological plots about Osiris (ancient Egypt), Adonis (Phoenicia), Dionysus (Greece), Siovush (Central Asia) were created in this way. During the gradual development of human thinking, mythology, which consisted of only the simplest primitive beliefs in its first stage of development, became a perfect system containing a series of mythical plots, mythical images and imaginations about the universe, society and nature.

Ancient forms of social consciousness such as animism, totemism, and fetishism were closely related to mythology. Mythology, formed as a primitive worldview system, is the first buds of ancient religious beliefs, the philosophical, moral and social views of our ancestors, the simplest concepts of the universe and human life, symbolic and metaphorical images built on the basis of unconscious-emotional understanding of reality, as well as the art of words, encompassing a system of rituals and various forms of mythological thought. It served as the leading idea of the primitive ideology as a coherent system that included the imagination and views of the ancient man on the perception of the universe. Mythology is a syncretic phenomenon that embodies the views of primitive man. Therefore, mythology served as a ground for the formation of folklore, written literature, art and spiritual values. Ancient myths, which reflect the struggle of the forces of goodness against the evil that created chaos (darkness), played an important role in the formation of artistic thinking. When the tradition of perceiving reality as an aesthetic category and interpreting it with the help of artistic words arose, the main part of ancient myths was absorbed into various genres of verbal art. The genetic roots of many epic plots and traditional motifs in the Uzbek folk art creativity go directly to the layer of mythological imagination. Myths played an important role in the creation of great artistic monuments such as "Avesta", "Iliad", "Ramayana", "Shahnoma", "Kalevala", "Alpomish", "Gorogli".

Many mythological characters with a mythological basis can be found in folk oral artistic creativity, written literature and works of art, because ancient mythological imaginations and mythical plots have served as a kind of inspiration in the formation and development of artistic thinking. Such images, based on mythological imagination, are the fruit of the folk imagination and the tradition of fantastic interpretation of reality. Mythical images are an animated symbolic expression of a specific event, and because they capture the essence of reality in a metaphorical, symbolic and metaphorical state, they are considered its formal embodiment. Mythical images are a product of primitive artistic

fiction and fantasy, which served to explain the causes of the origin of various phenomena in the universe, nature and society, as well as unusual forces existing in the imagination of ancient people. After the formation of artistic thinking, mythical images, which were considered a component of ancient mythology, moved to literature and art. Among these are the works of representatives of Uzbek classic literature, epics belonging to the series "Alpomish", "Kuntugmish", "Rustamkhan" and "Gorogli", mythological characters from Uzbek folk legends and tales. Mythical images in folklore and written literature serve as a full expression of artistic interpretation and show the comprehensiveness of poetic thinking.

A myth is one of the expressions of ancient people's beliefs, thoughts, religious views and first creative searches expressed through words. The myth was created by the specific needs of the spiritual world of primitive man, that is, the need to express his worldview. As the beginning of the tradition of artistic perception of reality, the system of mythological imagination formed in ancient times was the basis for the emergence of the plot series and composition of images of epic genres in folklore.

Therefore, the study of issues such as the essence, types, specific features, system of images, epic diffusion of mythological plots, and poetic tasks in folklore works are the main directions of mythology.

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